

Parenting Education for Career Development in Business Education: A Theoretical Review

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Abstract

Parenting education plays a crucial role in modeling the career development of students in Business Education. As primary influencers, parents contribute significantly to the career choices, motivation, and academic performance of their children. This paper examines the impact of parenting education on students' career development within the context of Business Education. It highlights how informed and supportive parenting practices such as career guidance, encouragement of entrepreneurial interests, exposure to business environments, and value-oriented upbringing can enhance students' decision-making and career readiness. The paper also examines the relationship between parents' socio-economic background, educational attainment, and their level of involvement in the career development process of their wards. This paper posits that informed parents are better equipped to support their children's pursuit of business education through access to relevant resources and encouragement. The paper recommends the integration of structured parenting education programme into school curricula and community initiatives to foster collaborative efforts between schools and families. By equipping parents with the necessary knowledge and skills, students in Business Education can be better guided towards fulfilling a productive career paths in business-related fields. This approach is essential for building a robust, entrepreneurial, and skilled workforce in a competitive global economy.

Keywords: Parenting Education, Career Development, Business Education

Introduction

In today's rapidly evolving global economy, the role of parenting extends far beyond nurturing personal values; it increasingly influences academic and career pathways, especially in specialized fields like business education. Parenting education, which equips parents with knowledge and skills to support their children's holistic development and choice of career paths, is gaining recognition as a critical factor in shaping future career success. Business education is defined by Ihekwaba (2017) as the type of education that assists individuals to acquire skills which can be applied to solve problems in business occupation. Family background plays a pivotal role in skill development. Factors such as parental support, exposure to entrepreneurial role models, and family values significantly influence a child's entrepreneurial mindset (Sanni, Aransi, & Abidemi 2024). These findings highlight the multifaceted ways in which parents can contribute to their children's entrepreneurial readiness

In order to have good results at school, the parental control over the child needs to be permanent. In order to have success within the educational activity, parents need to be familiar with some rules which are connected to the children physical development and psychological development. In the family there are these functioning elements, these are: love, marriage, the care and happiness, elements related to the functioning of life and the future. (Sanni, Aransi, & Abidemi 2024). Children have two main educators in their lives – their parents and their teachers. Parents are the prime educators until the child attends nursery or starts school and remain a major influence on their children's learning through school and beyond. According to BeqjaHamit, 2022, mother is always closer to children. Children always adopt parent's values and types of behaviour (Kasapi, Gjylmsere, 2013). However, if parents have positive influence on their children's everyday activities, and most importantly in their education, the future will be beautiful for the child.

Business education curriculum content is designed to deliver certain employability skills to students. Mufutau and Oladeji (2014) described business education as an aspect of education programme which prepares a student for career in business. It is an education needed to handle personal affairs and for a citizen to be able to become a good citizen of country. The intersection of parenting education and career development in business education, highlighting how informed and engaged parenting can foster ambition and career choice and development in business education as a course of study. Parental guidance can significantly impact a student's motivation, confidence, and career choices.

Concept of Parenting Education

Parenting education is a broad term referring to any effort to help parents become more effective in raising their children. It can involve various methods, including courses, workshops, support groups, and resources. According to Moran (2004), parenting education refers to any programme, service, or resources aimed at enhancing the knowledge, skills, and confidence of parents in order to improve parenting practices and child development outcomes. The goal of parenting education is to improve parenting practices, strengthen family relationships and promote positive child development.

Parents play an important role in the career aspirations of their children. The majority of the students follow career paths that are suggested or offered by their parents due to financial dependency, cultural values and respect for authority. Parental influence on career choice is generally based on the perception of the parents on job security, social status and economic stability as stated by Adetunji and Olaniyan (2020). Parents who have a business education or entrepreneurial orientation will more likely encourage their children to pursue business careers, exposing them to business activities at an early stage (Eze & Ugochukwu, 2019).

Types of Parenting Education

Parenting education encompasses various approaches and programmes aimed at supporting parents in their child-rearing journey. While there's no single, universally accepted definition, it generally involves providing parents with knowledge, skills and strategies to effectively nurture their children's development. This education can take many forms, from formal classes and workshops to informal support groups and online resources (Mufutau 2024).

Formal Parenting Classes and Workshops:

- Infant Care
- Child Development
- Discipline Strategies
- Parenting Style
- Special Needs
- Early Childhood Education

Informal Support and Resources

- Parenting Support Groups
- Online Parenting Communities

- Parenting Books and Articles
- Parenting Apps

Importance of Parenting Education

The following are the importance of parenting education according to Mufutau (2024):

- **Improved Communication:** Parenting education helps parents learn how to communicate effectively with their children, leading to better understanding and fewer misunderstandings.
- **Stronger family bonds:** by fostering positive interactions and strengthening relationships, parenting education contributes to a more supportive and nurturing family environment.
- **Enhance Child Development:** when parents are equipped with effective parenting skills, children are more likely to thrive in areas of physical, emotional, social and intellectual development.
- **Reduced challenges:** parenting education can also help parents navigate common challenges like infant crying, sleep issues and behavioural problems.

Parents are charged with the task of guiding the children from making wrong choices at the point of career selection in life. Given that parents are in a key position to positively affect children, yet they face significant challenges daily, to have positive parenting in a complex and ever-changing society, parenting education programmes should be designed to inspire, inform, and train parents.

The role of the woman or the mother as an educator represents a crucial resource to the development of the individual identity, which from researchers is seen even as more important as the very marital status of the parents and the occupation of the parents themselves. It seems that the feeling of being a mother, to the woman is more powerful than being a father of given child for the husband. Given the biological and physiological connection between mother and child, the maternal role constitutes the initial and essential phase of a child's developmental process. This is grounded in the fact that the mother not only gives birth but also provides the primary care and nurturing that guide the child from infancy toward eventual autonomy in adulthood. The mother's function in this regard, is a very important role which as such may be divided into two parts or directions: The Psychological protection, which can be reflected through the child's emotional security and psychological protection, especially in moments when the child feels it when the mother is next to him/her. Another group of activities in this regard, are the maternal functions regarding the child's development involving here

the physical development, the intellectual development as well as the emotional development of the child (Ango, 2024). Each child which grows up and is educated in the presence of mother, for sure is expected to reach an appropriate physical, psychological as well as social development. In this regard, these children have a much better appearance, they look happy and they enjoy the childhood in general. They are communicative and as such they are ready to cooperate (Alagbe (2023). For this reason, mother's love and care for the child, is full and well completed, and as such is often accepted by other members of the very family. This type of cultivated love and affection can be qualified as a key condition for an appropriate development of the children in a given family. Children experience physical as well as psychological effects of their mother, and as such they are taken as model which influences their further development during their emotional stage of development of their moral values as whole. This element of the so called child's identification, the child embeds it in his/her personality for years on and on, throughout his/her total lifespan. It is planted in their character as well as temperament, and as such it is reflected through his/ her attitudes and thoughts in interaction or behavior with the society in general. Almost all culture have developed arrangements which enable mothers to provide for basic child care while maintaining other duties that are instrumental to family wellbeing (Idoko, 2024) However, depending on the economic, social as well as emotional limitations, mothers, nowadays have a variety of opportunities to be able to influence the child's overall development and the choice of a career in life.

Father plays a critical role in the effective organization and functional development of the household, contributing significantly to the stability and wellbeing of the family unit with a specific accent on the children. The so called subjective experience of parents by their children varies in different ways and family models, and as such his relevance in a family is much more different from the one that is performed by mothers. As a result of the gender prejudices in terms of the duties to be performed in their family, especially regarding their approach and contribution towards their children's education, it turns out that mothers are more prepared to undertake their role in their children's education, rather than their fathers. Fathers make a powerful difference in defining expectation and challenging children to do their best (Idoko, 2024). As such, the children learn their responsibilities and role in the family, when they themselves grow up and become parents. There has been so many assertions, which proves that the relationship between father and child becomes stronger. This relationship is not different from neither of the other two relations that is, the one between father and

child neither the one between mother and child (Ango,2024). In order to have a successfully brought up and well educated children in one family, parents are crucial and they must be careful to some elements which play a key role in raising, bringing up and educating their children; Firstly, while the parent's principal role in the family is the education, career guidance and the bringing up of their children, then the main obligation of their children is to study harder and properly. For this aim, they need to be well instructed how to study, based upon rules and principles of an appropriate learning and studying. This approach would open to them the doors of the world of a behaviorist attitude towards the work, making possible for them to get to know better the relevance of working as one of the main behaviorist elements of the human kind. Secondly, the development of the child is in fact an overall child's personality formation. Parents as educators must be able to recognize the basic features of their child, interests, temperament especially the child's emotional features regarding the child's character. This will in turn help them to guide the children in the selection of a career path. Thirdly, the child's personality formation has resulted to be constructed mostly based upon child's socialization in general. The socialization process nowadays represents the most important one of all other processes involved in the development of a child.

The concept of Business Education

Oyedeji, Ajao and Omotade (2019) described Business Education as an important part of the general education with emphasis on skills and competencies acquisition for use in offices and business related occupations. According to Aliyu (2013), accounting option of Business Education aims at producing well qualified and competent graduates in accounting who will be able to teach accounting and other business related courses and also work in accounting firms. Students with specialty in this option will be taught courses like; Cost accounting and Management accounting, Advanced Financial accounting, Taxation, Auditing, Statistics, Business Communication and so on, they would have been properly groomed to teach accounting effectively and also work in account section of any office after graduation. Distributive education option of business education is to equip graduates with the right skills that will enable them engage in the marketing sector of the economy so also to be able to teach all marketing courses and other business related courses. Students in this option will be taught courses like; Principles of Marketing, Commerce, Monetary Economics, Principles of Management, and so on they would have had appreciable knowledge of the global market situation and how to break into the market with whatever they intend to introduce to their clients. Office Technology and Management

Option (OTM (Office Education) aims at equipping students with necessary competencies so as to qualify as professional secretaries and competent OTM educators. Students will be equipped with skills that will qualify them to work for others and themselves. After receiving this training they will be able to manipulate any office machine and function well as teachers of the course. They will be taught courses like; Office Management, Office Technology and Management, Principles of Management, Computer Application, Business Communication and so on. After this training, they will be employable and can also become employers of labour.

Objectives of Business Education

Federal Republic of Nigeria in its Minimum Standard for Nigerian Colleges of Education (2020) stated the objectives of business education as:

1. To produce well qualified and competent graduates who will teach business subjects in secondary schools and other related institutions
2. To produce business teachers who will be able to inculcate the vocational aspects of Business Education into the society
3. To produce business teachers who will be involved in the more desired revolution of vocational development right from the primary through secondary schools.
4. To equip students with necessary competencies so as to qualify them for a post degree programme in Business Education
5. To equip graduates with the right skills that will enable them to engage in a life of work in the office as well for self-employment.

Career opportunities in Business Education

There are four options in the Business Education programme. The following are career opportunities available in each options according to Colleges of Education Minimum Standard for Vocational and Technical Education (2020) (Adegbokiki, 2024).

Accounting Education Option

* Providing auditing services for small businesses * Recording books of accounts for small business firms * Training book keepers * Organizing seminars/workshops on book keeping and Accounts for

small business firms and schools. * Rendering accounting programme and software for clients * Teaching accounting in schools

Office Technology and Management Option

* Office/Secretarial services providers (Business Centers) * Printing and Publishing – books and stickers * Consultancy services * Database management experts * Computer/system maintenance/services * Bulletin board services * Running a computer training school

Marketing Education Option

* E-commerce specialist * Selling of office stationeries * Marketing advisory services * Salesmanship services * E-marketing * Providing rental services

Entrepreneurship Education Option

* Packaging and rebranding of products * Products retailing * Operating a small scale business * organizing vocational training and seminars.

Influence of Parenting Education on the choice of Business Education as a Career

According to Alika (2010) parenting plays a crucial role in shaping a child's values, interest and career aspirations. In recent years, there has been growing recognition of the impact that parenting education programs and strategies that equip parents with effective child-rearing skills can have on children's academic and career choices. One area where this influence is increasingly evident is in students' decision to pursue business education as a career path.

Parenting education helps parents become more aware of the importance of nurturing their children's talents and guiding them through informed decision-making. Educated parents are more likely to expose their children to diverse career opportunities, including business related fields. As a result, children raised by parents who have undergone some form of parenting education may develop a greater awareness of the relevance and benefits of business education, such as entrepreneurship, financial literacy and managerial skills (Anthonia, 2017).

Esters & Bowen (2005) asserts that parenting education often encourages supportive and democratic parenting styles, where children are allowed to express their interests and receive guidance rather than pressure. This environment fosters self-confidence and a sense of autonomy in career choice. In such households, if a child expresses interest in business, the parent is more likely to

encourage this interest by providing access to resources, mentorship, or extracurricular programs that align with business education.

Additionally, parents who understand modern economic trends and employment demands-knowledge often emphasized in parenting education-are more inclined to promote careers in fields with promising prospects. Business education, being closely tied to real-world applications and entrepreneurial success, naturally becomes a favoured recommendation for future-oriented parents.

Parenting education can significantly influence a child's decision to pursue business education by fostering awareness, support, and informed guidance. As such, promoting parenting education could be a valuable strategy in helping students make empowered and strategic career choices in the competitive global economy (Anthonia, 2017).

Conclusion

Parenting education plays a vital role in shaping children's career paths, particularly in the field of business education. Through informed parenting practices, parents become more effective in guiding their children toward careers that align their strengths, interests and the demands of the modern economy. By fostering open communication, encouraging exploration, and providing access to relevant resources, parenting education equips families to support informed and confident career decisions. As business education continues to grow in relevance due to globalization and entrepreneurship, the role of educated, proactive parenting becomes even more essential. Promoting parenting education is therefore, a strategic approach to nurturing the next generation of business educators and leaders.

Recommendation

The following recommendations were raised:

1. Government and the Ministry of education should Incorporate Career Guidance into Parenting Education Programmes
2. School Administrators should integrate structured parenting education programmes into school curricula and community initiatives

3. Stakeholders' should encourage early exposure of students to business concepts
4. Parents and school counselors should promote open communication about career interest
5. Institutions should connect parents with educational and career resources
6. Stakeholders' foster parent-school collaboration
7. Policy makers should tailor programmes to different socioeconomic background

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